

Studies in Linear Furocoumarins. Part II* New Syntheses of Psoralen** and 3-Methylpsoralen

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A new synthesis of psoralen and 3-methylpsoralen has been achieved. The latter has also been synthesised by building a furan ring on 6-acetylbumbelliferone.

Linear furocoumarins are a well known group of natural substances, most of which are effective skin photosensitizing agents¹. Psoralen (I) is the simplest member of this group of compounds having high photodynamic activity².

Although an effective method for the extraction of psoralen from the seeds of *Psoralea corylifolia* Linn. has been devised in our laboratory³, we felt the necessity to study its synthesis from the cheap raw material resorcinol.

A few syntheses of psoralen are already known⁴⁻⁷ but these involve a large number of steps and the overall yield from resorcinol never exceeds 10%. In this paper we are reporting a new method for the synthesis of psoralen involving only 5 steps with 15% overall yield starting from resorcinol. 6-Acetoxy coumaran⁶ (IIa) was condensed with acrylonitrile using anhydrous zinc chloride and hydrogen chloride gas as condensing agents to produce 2,3,5,6-tetrahydropsoresalen (III). The latter compound was dehydrogenated with palladised charcoal in boiling diphenyloxide to produce psoralen. The synthetic sample had identical m.p. (mixed m.p. undepressed) and U.V. spectra with those of natural psoralen.

The scheme for building up a pyrone ring is quite general and has been much used in our laboratory⁸⁻¹⁰. The synthesis of 3-methyl-psoralen, which possesses about 67% photosensitizing activity of psoralen² was accomplished in 55% overall yield from 3-methyl-6-hydroxycoumaran (IIb). IIb was synthesised in 5 steps from resorcinol according to the method of Foster *et al.*⁵ Resacetophenone was partially benzylated and the product

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** A preliminary communication appeared in *Science and Culture*, 1967, **33**, 528.

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after condensation with ethyl bromoacetate and hydrolysis, was cyclised to 3-methyl-6-benzyloxybenzofuran (IV). Hydrogenation with palladised charcoal resulted in IIb. IIb was condensed with acrylonitrile at 0–5° using zinc chloride and dry hydrogen chloride as condensing agents to produce 3-methyl-2,3,5,6-tetrahydropsovalen (IIIa). IIIa on dehydrogenation with 10% palladised charcoal gave 3-methylpsoralen (Ia) identical in all respects with the compound synthesised by building up a furan ring over coumarin as described below.

6-Acetyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (VI), prepared in 3-steps from resorcinol⁸, was condensed with ethyl bromoacetate to produce 6-acetyl-7-[carbethoxy]-methyloxy coumarin (VII). It was hydrolysed to the corresponding acid VIIa. The acid was heated with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate to give a product which after purification by vacuum sublimation and crystallisation gave 3-methylpsoralen. The overall yield of 3-methylpsoralen in the former method is much higher.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are uncorrected. The compounds were repeatedly crystallised from the solvents until sharp and constant melting points and single spot TLC were obtained. The infrared spectra were determined as Nujol mulls. UV spectra were measured in an ethanol solution.

2,3,5,6-Tetrahydropsovalen (III): Dry hydrogen chloride was bubbled through a well stirred mixture of 6-acetoxy-2,3-dihydrobenzofuran (1.78 g; 0.01 mole), anhydrous zinc chloride (1.36 g; 0.01 mole), acrylonitrile (0.64 g; 0.012 mole) and sodium dried ether (40 ml) maintaining the temperature between 0–5°. A clear solution resulted and then a reddish layer separated. Hydrogen chloride was bubbled through for 3 hrs. more maintaining the

same temperature. The reaction mixture was left for 48 hrs., in the dark. The layer was separated from ether by decantation and washed with 25 ml of ether. The oily product after treatment with water (15 ml) was heated over a steam-bath for 30 mins. The crude product obtained on cooling, was purified by sublimation (210°/0.9 mm). Crystallisation from ethanol yielded 1.2 g (60%) of 2,3,5,6-tetrahydropsovalen, m.p. 154° (Found : C, 69.56; H, 5.00. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires : C, 69.46; H, 5.30) The I.R. spectra showed band at 1775 cm^{-1} (lactone).

Psoralen (I) : A mixture of 2,3,5,6-tetrahydropsovalen (1 g; 0.005 mole), 10% Pd/C (1.0 g) and diphenyl oxide (15 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 hrs. The catalyst was removed from the hot solution. Removal of diphenyl oxide by distillation under reduced pressure afforded 0.5 g (50%) of crystalline solid which melted at 161–162° after crystallisation from benzene (lit³, m.p. 161–162°). Mixed melting point with natural psoralen remained undepressed. (Found C, 71.18; H, 3.52. for $C_{11}H_8O_3$: C, 70.97; H, 3.32). U.V. spectrum showed bands at 246, 290 and 328 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.37, 4.03 and 3.80 respectively).

6-Acetyl-7-[carbethoxy]-methyloxycoumarin (VII) : A mixture of 6-acetyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (3.4 g; 0.0175 mole), anhydrous potassium carbonate (7 g; 0.05 mole), ethyl bromoacetate (4.0 g; 0.025 mole) and dry acetone (40 ml) was stirred and refluxed for 24 hrs. Potassium carbonate was filtered off. The filtrate on removal of solvent gave 3.5 g (73%) of 6-acetyl-7-[carbethoxy]-methyloxycoumarin (VII) which melted after crystallisation from ethyl acetate at 159°. (Found : C, 62.28; H, 4.81; $C_{15}H_{14}O_6$ requires : C, 62.06; H, 4.68). The I.R. spectrum shows bands at 1625 (unsaturation), 1670 (ketone), 1720 (coumarin), 1760 (ester) cm^{-1} .

6-Acetyl-7-[carboxy]-methyloxycoumarin (VIIa) : A mixture of VII (2.9 g; 0.01 mole) and 5% 1 : 1 methanolic caustic potash (100 ml) was kept in dark for 24 hrs. A clear solution obtained was then refluxed on water-bath for 4 hrs. and methanol distilled off. The residue on acidification gave a solid which on crystallisation from ethanol yielded 1.4 g. (54%) of 6-acetyl-7-[carboxy]-methyloxycoumarin (VIIa), m.p. 235–36°. (Found : C, 59.20; H, 3.48. $C_{13}H_{10}O_6$ requires : C, 59.54; H, 3.84).

3-Methylpsoralen (Ia) : A mixture of VIIa (0.52 g; 0.002 mole), acetic anhydride (5 ml) and fused sodium acetate (1.5 g) was heated under reflux at 150–5° for 0.5 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into crushed ice. The precipitated solid on crystallisation from ethyl acetate-pet.-ether (40–60°) yielded 0.30 g. (75%) 3-methylpsoralene (Ia) m.p. 189° (lit.,¹¹ m.p. 189°) (Found : C, 71.97; H, 3.88. $C_{12}H_8O_3$ requires : C, 71.99; H, 4.03).

3-Methyl tetrahydropsovalen (IIIa) : Dry hydrogen chloride was bubbled through a mixture of 6-hydroxy-3-methyl-2,3-dihydrobenzofuran (IIb) (1 g; 0.007 mole), zinc chloride (0.94 g; 0.007 mole), acrylonitrile (0.53 g; 0.01 mole) and Na-dried ether (25 ml) at 0°. The mixture was stirred vigorously. After half an hour, a reddish oily layer that separated turned blue after passing the gas for 30 mins. more. The ethereal solution was saturated with hydrogen chloride and the reaction mixture was left for 48 hrs. After removal of the

ether layer by decantation, the residual oil was decomposed with water (10 ml) by heating over a steam-bath for 1 hr., extracted with ether, solvent removed and the residue on vacuum sublimation (210°, 0.8 mm) gave 1 g. (75%) of 3-methyl tetrahydropsovalen (IIIa). It crystallised from pet.-ether (40–60°) melted at 82–3° (Found : C, 70.44; H, 5.78. C₁₂H₁₂O₃ requires : C, 70.57; H, 5.92). I.R. spectrum showed band at 1755 cm⁻¹ (lactone).

3-Methylpsoralen (Ia) : A mixture of 3-methyl tetrahydropsovalen (0.4 g; 0.002 mole), 10% Pd/C (0.4 g) and diphenyl oxide (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 hrs. The catalyst was removed from the hot solution, diphenyl oxide distilled off under reduced pressure when 0.36 g. (90%) of crystalline solid, m.p. 189° after recrystallisation from ethylacetate-pet. ether (b.p. 40–60°) was obtained. Melting point (m.m.p. undepressed), U.V. and I.R. spectra are identical with product obtained by the previous method. I.R. bands at ν_{max} 1710 cm⁻¹ (coumarin), U.V. bands at λ_{max} 219, 249, 292, 330 (log ϵ 4.26, 4.42, 4.13 and 3.83 respectively).

The authors are grateful to Mr. P. Bagchi, Director of Research, East India Pharmaceutical Works Ltd., Calcutta and Dr. S. K. Das Gupta for their kind interest and valuable suggestions.

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Received April 12, 1969